

Research Article

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SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION AND *IN-SILICO* EVALUATION OF SOME AMINO SUBSTITUTED PHENYLHYDROXAMIC ACID LIGANDS AS POTENTIAL ANTIBIOTICS: DRUG LIKENESS AND MOLECULAR DOCKING STUDIES

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ABSTRACT

Some Amino Substituted Phenylhydroxamic Acid Ligand (2-aminophenyl hydroxamic acid (L1H2), 4-aminophenyl hydroxamic acid (L2H2), 4-amino-2-methoxyhydroxamic acid (L3H2) and (E)-N-hydroxy-4-((2-hydroxybenzylidene)amino)benzamide (L4H3) have been synthesized and characterized on the basis of solubility, conductivity, melting point determination, microanalysis, infrared and NMR spectroscopies. Antimicrobial activity of the compounds has also been evaluated against selected Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial strains as well as fungal specie (*Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans*). *In silico* molecular docking and ADMET studies were also employed. The results indicate successful formation of the ligands. The solubility results indicate that the ligands are soluble in polar solvents (water, methanol, ethanol) but insoluble in non-polar solvents like n-hexane and benzene. The elemental analysis results confirm the stoichiometry of the compounds. The antimicrobial study results reveals that the ligands 2-aminophenyl hydroxamic acid and 4-aminophenyl hydroxamic acid showed considerable activity against *candida albican* with zone of inhibition of 35.0±0.0 and 30.0±0.0 mm respectively at concentration of 30 mg/mL, while the ligand 4-amino-2-methoxyphenyl hydroxamic acid presented zone of inhibition of 20.4±0.2, and 20.1±0.1 mm at concentration of 30 and 20 mg/mL respective against *S. aureus*. The control drugs show slightly better antimicrobial activity than the best of the ligands. The ADMET studies reveal that all the ligands displayed acceptable drug-likeness with no Lipinski violations, moderate-to-high predicted oral absorption, and favourable hERG inhibition profiles. Among the ligands, 2-aminophenyl emerged as the most promising candidate due to its superior solubility and comparatively higher permeability. Molecular docking of the three ligands into the *Staphylococcus aureus* protein target (PDB ID: 3G7B) revealed distinct binding modes with total scores ranged from -5.735 to -5.032, L3H2 showing the strongest affinity and L1H2 the weakest. For *Candida albicans* protein target propargyl-linked antifolate (PDB ID: 4HOE), the ligand 2-aminophenyl hydroxamic acid (L1H2) yielded a docking score of -4.815 while Ligand 4-aminophenyl hydroxamic acid (L2H2) produced slightly weaker docking score of -4.626. Ligand 4-amino-2-methoxyphenyl hydroxamic acid (L3H2) exhibited the most favourable docking score of -5.659, representing the strongest binding affinity in the series. It is worth noting that the docking scores for both 2-aminophenyl and 4-aminophenyl hydroxamic acids (-4.815 and -4.626, respectively) also fall within a range that may be considered for initial screening hits.

Keywords: Synthesis, Characterization, Hydroxamic acid, ADMET, *In silico* molecular docking

INTRODUCTION

Hydroxamic acids are well-established naturally occurring and synthetic weak organic acids that feature both an amide group and a hydroxylamine functional group [1,2,3]. Hydroxamic acids and their derivatives fulfil a variety of important biological roles as inhibitors of metalloenzymes metabolites of bacteria and fungi [4,5,6]. Due to the electron-donating capabilities of the nitrogen and oxygen atoms, hydroxamic acids are being investigated for their ability to bind and remove metal pollutants from contaminated water [7,8,9,10].

In particular, hydroxamic acids among the numerous ligands used in metal coordination are known for their ability to form stable complexes which has made them useful for use in drug design, especially for anti-bacteria or anti-cancer therapies [2,11]. The ability of hydroxamic acids to bind tightly to metal ions, enables the design of effective enzyme inhibitors and biomolecular probes. Studies suggest that these complexes may exhibit anticancer activity by inhibiting specific metalloenzymes involved in cell proliferation and metastasis. Moreover, their antimicrobial properties make them potential candidates for developing new drugs to combat bacterial infections [12,13].

The amino substituted hydroxamic acid ligands, with their amino groups, offer an interesting structural platform for metal binding [1,14,15]. The introduction of additional functional groups, such as amino and methoxy groups in the hydroxamic acid ligands are expected to alter the electronic environment of the ligand, influencing both the coordination with metal ions and the solubility, stability as well as the reactivity of the resulting complexes [5,16,17,18].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

All the chemicals and reagents used for the synthesis were of analytical grade, purchased from Sigma Aldrich and were used without further purification. These include: hydroxylamine sulphate, methyl 2-aminobenzoate, methyl 4-aminobenzoate, methyl 4- amino-2-methoxybenzoate, 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde, Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH), Tetraoxosulphate(VI) acid (H₂SO₄), deionized water (ice) and sodium sulphate.

Synthesis of the ligands

2-(amino)phenylhydroxamic acid ligand (L1H2)

The preparation of 2-(amino)phenylhydroxamic acid was carried out according to literature procedure [1]. To an aqueous solution of NaOH (7.40 g, 185 mmol, 30 cm³), 30.03 g of ice and hydroxylamine sulphate (6.10 g, 37 mmol) were added, followed by Na₂SO₄ (0.58 g, 4.44 mmol) and methyl 2-aminobenzoate (5.60 g, 4.8 cm³, 37 mmol). The reaction mixture was stirred at 45°C for 24 h (Scheme 1). The solution was then allowed to cool and the pH was adjusted to 6 using 10% H₂SO₄. At this point a light pink solid precipitate out of the solution and it was allowed to stir for another 15 mins. The solid was then filtered and dried via vacuum filtration to give a yield of 65.4% (3.69g).

Elemental analysis (%) calculated as L1H2 (C₇H₈N₂O₂): C 55.26, H 5.30, N 18.41. Found: C 54.52, H 5.36, N 17.77. ¹H NMR (400 MHz d₆-DMSO): δ 2.5 ((CD₃)₂SO residual solvent peak), 3.4 (s, H₂O), 6.2 (s, 2H, NH₂), 6.5-7.4 (m, 4H, Ar-H), 8.9 (s, 1H, NH), 10.9 (s, 1H, OH).

¹³C NMR (400 MHz, DMSO): δ (ppm) = 167.4 (CO), 149.6 (C, Ar), 132.1 (CH, Ar), 127.9 (CH, Ar), 116.6 (CH, Ar), 115.2 (CH, Ar), 113.5 (CH, Ar).

MS: m/z (% Rel. Ab.): 152 (48) [M⁺], 136 (40) [M⁺ - OH], 120 (100) [M⁺ - NH₂OH].

FT-IR (cm⁻¹): 3403(sh), 3323 (w), 3171 (m), 2972 (w), 2863(m), 1636(sh), 1562(w), 1495(w), 1450(w), 1348(w), 1250(w), 1131(sh, s), 1021 (m, sh), 947 (w), 901 (w), 872 (w), 683 (w), 639 (w), 617 (m, sh), 419 (m).

Scheme 1: Preparation of 2-(amino)phenylhydroxamic acid (L1H2)

4-(amino)phenyl hydroxamic acid ligand (L2H2)

Hydroxylamine sulphate (6.10 g, 37mmol) and 30.03 g of ice were added to an aqueous solution of NaOH (7.41 g, 185 mmol, 30 cm³). Na₂SO₄ (0.58 g, 4.44 mmol) and methy-4- aminobenzoate (5.70 g, 37 mmol) were then added to

the solution. The mixture was subsequently stirred at 45°C for 24 hrs ((Scheme 2). The resultant solution was allowed to cool and the pH was adjusted to 6 using H₂SO₄. When the pH reached 6, a solid precipitated out of the solution. When the pH reached 6, a beige colour solid precipitated out of the solution. The solid was then collected via filtration and recrystallized from hot water and cooled with ice to give L2H2 in 60 % yield (3.39 g). Elemental analysis (%) calculated as L2H2 (C₇H₈N₂O₂): C 55.26, H 5.30, N 18.42. Found: C 55.24, H 5.53, N 18.10.

¹H NMR (400 MHz d₆-DMSO): δ 2.5 ((CD₃)₂SO residual solvent peak), 3.4 (s, H₂O), 5.5 (s, 2H, NH₂), 6.5 (d, *J* = 8.5 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 7.4 (d, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 2H, Ar-H), 8.6 (s, 1H, NH), 10.7 (s, 1H, OH).

¹³C NMR (400 MHz, DMSO): δ (ppm) = 165.5 (CO), 152.0 (C, Ar), 128.7 (2CH, Ar), 119.6 (C, Ar), 113.1 (2CH, Ar).

FT-IR (cm⁻¹): 3410(s, sh), 3332 (m), 3274 (br), 3025(m), 2789(m), 1645(s, sh), 1589 (s, sh), 1556 (s, sh), 1535 (s, sh), 1502 (s, sh), 1405 (s, sh), 1321 (sh, s), 1292 (sh, s), 1188 (sh, s), 1157 (sh, s), 1094 (sh, s), 1023 (sh, s), 895 (sh, s), 832 (sh, s), 746 (sh, s), 694 (sh, s), 638 (m, sh), 567 (s), 520 (sh), 469 (s, sh), 422 (sh).

MS-EI: m/z (% Rel. Ab.): 152 (8, {M⁺}), 134 (8, {M- OH}⁺), 120 (100, {M- NHOH}⁺).

Scheme 2: Synthesis of 4-(amino)phenyl hydroxamic acid (L2H2)

Synthesis of 4-amino-2-methoxyphenyl hydroxamic acid ligand (L3H2)

Hydroxylamine sulphate (6.10 g, 37mmol) and 30.03 g of ice were added to an aqueous solution of NaOH (7.41 g, 185 mmol, 30 cm³). Na₂SO₄ (0.58 g, 4.44 mmol) and methy-4-amino-2-methoxybenzoate (6.70 g, 37 mmol) were then added to the solution. The mixture was subsequently stirred at 45°C for 24 hrs (Scheme 3). The resultant solution was allowed to cool and the pH was adjusted to 6 using H₂SO₄ to initiate the precipitation of a pink solid. The solid was then collected via filtration and recrystallized from hot water and cooled with ice to give L₃H₂ in 69% yield (4.64 g).

Elemental analysis (%) calculated as L₃H₂ (C₈H₁₀N₂O₃): C 52.75, H 5.53, N 15.38. Found: C 53.07, H 5.43, N 15.02. FT-IR (cm⁻¹): 3343 (s), 3316 (m), 3220 (m), 2831 (w), 1619 (s), 1594 (s), 1527 (s), 1497 (s), 1468 (s), 1459 (s), 1427 (s), 1335 (s), 1278 (s), 1260 (s), 1212 (s), 1192 (s), 1156 (s), 1118 (s), 1025 (s), 955 (s), 889 (s), 849 (s), 828 (m), 771 (s), 738 (s), 717 (w), 644 (s), 611 (s), 546 (s), 525 (s).

MS-EI: m/z (% Rel. Ab.): 182 (8, {M⁺}), 166 (28, {M- H₂N}⁺), 150 (100, {M- NHOH}⁺).

¹H NMR (400 MHz DMSO-*d*₆): δ 2.5 ((CD₃)₂SO residual solvent peak), 3.7 (s, 3H, OMe), 5.6 (s, NH₂), 6.2 (m, Ar), 7.5 (d, H, Ar-H), 8.7 (s, 1H, Ar-H), 10.11 (s, 1H, OH).

¹³C NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ (ppm) = 164.4 (CO), 158.8 (C, Ar), 153.3 (CH, Ar), 132.3 (CH, Ar), 108.3 (CH, Ar), 106.4 (CH, Ar), 96.3 (C, Ar), 55.6 (C-OMe).

Scheme 3: Synthesis of 4-amino-2-methoxy hydroxamic acid (L3H3)

Synthesis of (E)-N-hydroxy-4-((2-hydroxybenzylidene)amino)benzamide (L4H3)

4-(amino)phenylhydroxamic acid (1.00 g, 6.57 mmol) and salicylaldehyde (0.80 g, 6.57 mmol) were dissolved in dry methanol (30 cm³) and refluxed at 70°C for 3 hours to give yellow precipitate. The solution was allowed to cool and the precipitate filtered and air dried under suction to give yield of 58% (0.56 g). Elemental analysis (%) calculated as L4H3 (C₁₄H₁₂N₂O₃): C 65.62, H 4.72, N 10.93. Found: C 65.67, H 4.57, N 10.58.

¹H NMR (400 MHz d₆-DMSO): δ 2.51 ((CD₃)₂SO residual solvent peak), 7.00 (t, 2H, Ar-H), 7.44 (d, 1H, Ar-H), 7.49 (d, 2H, Ar-H), 7.70 (d, 1H, Ar-H), 7.88 (d, 2H, Ar-H), 8.99 (s, 1H, CH=N), 9.08 (s, 1H, NH), 11.28 (s, 1H, OH), 12.85 (s, 1H, OH).

¹³C NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆): δ (ppm) = 164.9 (CO), 164.1 (C=N), 160.7 (C, Ar), 151.0 (C, Ar), 134.2 (CH, Ar), 130.1 (CH, Ar), 131.3 (C, Ar), 128.7 (2CH, Ar), 121.8 (2CH, Ar), 119.7 (C, Ar), 119.7 (CH, Ar), 117.1 (CH, Ar).

MS-EI: m/z (% Rel. Ab.): 256.08 (20; {M}⁺), 240.23 (24; {M - OH}⁺), 224.32 (100, {M - H₂NO}⁺), 196.43 (16, {M - CH₂NO₂}⁺), 77.37 (04, {C₆H₆}⁺).

FT-IR (cm⁻¹): 3275 (s), 3026 (br), 2699 (br), 1644 (m), 1617 (w), 1598 (s), 1559 (s, sh), 1489 (s, sh), 1455 (m), 1437 (w), 1409 (m), 1363 (m), 1330 (m), 1309 (w), 1283 (s, sh), 1190 (s), 1181 (w), 1157 (s), 1033 (s), 1011 (s), 982 (s), 910 (w), 899 (s), 848 (s, sh), 779 (m), 750 (s, sh), 740 (w), 698 (m), 683 (m), 541 (w), 525 (s), 481 (s), 442 (s).

Scheme 3: Synthesis of (E)-N-hydroxy-4-((2-hydroxybenzylidene)amino)benzamide (L4H3)

Physical Measurement

Melting points were determined using Reichert-Jung Thermovar hot-stage microscope and were uncorrected. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were obtained at room temperature (298 K) on a Bruker Avance 400 Plus spectrometer with Sample Xpress, operating at 400 MHz (for ¹H) or 100 MHz (for ¹³C). Chemical shifts are reported in ppm and referenced to DMSO-d₆ (δH: 2.50 ppm, δC: 39.52 ppm). Elemental analysis was carried out at OEA Laboratories (Kelly Bray, Cornwall). Infra-red spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer FT-IR *Spectrum 100* spectrometer. Mass spectra (MS) were carried out on a Waters Acquity UPLC Synapt G2 HD mass spectrometer.

Antimicrobial evaluation

The ligands and standard drugs were evaluated for antimicrobial activity against Gram-positive bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus pyogenes*), Gram-negative bacteria (*Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Salmonella typhi*), and fungal species including *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans*, as outlined in the literature [19]. Microbial isolates were uniformly inoculated onto agar plates and then incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours for bacteria and 48 hours for fungi. Subsequently, paper discs loaded with various concentrations of the standard and synthesized compounds were placed on the plates. The effect of the compounds on the organisms was assessed by measuring the inhibition zones expressed in millimetres [20]. The experiment was repeated three times, and the results are presented as means with standard deviations.

ADMET Prediction

In silico ADMET (Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Excretion, and Toxicity) profiling of the four compounds (4-aminophenyl hydroxamic acid, 4-amino-2-methoxyhydroxamic acid, 2-aminophenyl hydroxamic acid and N-hydroxy-4-((2-hydroxybenzylidene)amino)benzamide (L4H3) was performed using Schrödinger Maestro version 13.4 (Schrödinger, LLC, New York, NY, USA). Three-dimensional structures of the ligands were constructed using the Maestro 2D sketcher and prepared with the LigPrep module, which generated low-energy conformers using the OPLS3e force field at physiological pH (7.0 ± 2.0) with Epik for ionization state prediction. The prepared ligands were then submitted to the QikProp module (version 6.1) in normal mode to predict key pharmacokinetic and toxicity descriptors, including molecular weight (mol MW), polar surface area (PSA), lipophilicity (QPlogPo/w), aqueous solubility (QPlogS), Caco-2 and MDCK permeability (QPPCaco, QPPMDCK), percentage human oral absorption (%HOA), blood-brain barrier partitioning (QPlogBB), CNS activity score, hERG inhibition risk (QPlogHERG), and Lipinski Rule of Five violations. All calculations were performed using default QikProp settings, and the predicted parameters were evaluated against established drug-likeness thresholds to assess the developability of each compound.

Molecular Docking

Molecular docking of the four ligands (4-aminophenyl hydroxamic acid, 4-amino-2-methoxyhydroxamic acid, 2-aminophenyl hydroxamic acid and 2-((5-bromo-2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzyl)amino)-N-hydroxybenzamide) into the targeted receptor site of corresponding receptors was performed using Schrödinger Maestro version 13.4 (Schrödinger, LLC, New York, NY, USA). The three-dimensional crystal structures of the target proteins were retrieved from the Protein Data Bank (PDB IDs: 3G7B for *Staphylococcus aureus* and 4HOE for *Candida albicans*). Protein preparation was carried out using the Protein Preparation Wizard module, which included assigning bond orders, adding hydrogen

atoms, optimizing hydrogen bonding networks using the PROPKA algorithm at pH 7.0, and performing a restrained energy minimization using the OPLS3e force field to relieve steric clashes. The prepared ligands from the LigPrep step were used as input for docking. The receptor grid was generated around the native ligand binding site for each protein, with the grid box centered on the co-crystallized inhibitor to ensure accurate sampling of the active site.

Docking was performed using the Glide module (version 8.1) in Standard Precision (SP) mode, with default scaling factors for van der Waals radii (0.8) and partial atomic charges (0.15) to account for receptor flexibility. For each ligand, up to five docking poses were retained, and the best-scoring pose was selected based on the Glide docking score (G-score), which incorporates contributions from hydrogen bonding, hydrophobic interactions, electrostatic forces, and desolvation penalties. The docking results, including docking scores and interacting residues, were visualized and analyzed using the Maestro graphical interface to assess hydrogen bond geometries, π - π stacking interactions, and solvent exposure patterns [21,22].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Synthesis, Physical Characteristics and Analytical Data for the Hydroxamic Acid Ligands

Herein we describe the synthesis of the ligands 2-aminophenylhydroxamic acid (L1H2), 4-aminophenyl hydroxamic acid (L2H2), 4-amino-2-methoxyhydroxamic (L3H2) and N-hydroxy-4-((2-hydroxybenzylidene)amino)benzamide (L4H3)

Ligands L1H2, L2H2, L3H2 and L4H3 were synthesised according to literature method [1], by equimolar reaction of methyl 2-aminobenzoate, methyl 4-aminobenzoate or methyl 4-amino-2-methoxybenzoate and hydroxylamine sulphate. This reaction was carried out under alkaline condition. A small amount of disodium sulphate was added to accelerate the reaction. The desired products were recovered in pure form and in high yield (65%, 60% and 69% for L1H2, L2H2 and L3H2 respectively) (Table 1). The reaction is not fast and requires 24 hours for completion in most cases. However, this method can also be successfully applied on a large scale. Akin to ligands L1H2, L2H2 and L3H2 ligands, L4H3 was forged through the Schiff base coupling of 4-amino-phenylhydroxamic acid and bromo-vanillin. The reaction pathways for the synthesis of the ligands are shown in Scheme 1, 2, 3 and 4.

The Ligands were subsequently characterised using nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), infrared spectroscopy (IR) and mass spectrometry (MS) (See experimental section for details).

Spectroscopic Studies

NMR spectroscopy is one of the important tools that are used for the elucidation and authentication of molecular structures [23]. It provides information regarding the chemical environment and interaction of atoms within a given molecule. To validate the formation of the compounds, ^1H and $^{13}\text{C}\{\text{H}\}$ NMR were investigated on a 500 MHz and 125 MHz spectrometer using DMSO- d_6 as a solvent at room temperature. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the ligands were obtained, and are given in Fig. 1–4.

The ^1H NMR spectrum of L1H2 showed a singlet signal at 3.4 ppm associated with the NH_2 group, while two doublets at 7.46 and 6.71 ppm and two triplets at 6.50 and 7.30 ppm were assigned to the aromatic protons. Singlets at 8.90 ppm corresponding to protons belonging to the amide. The hydroximate OH groups appeared downfield at 10.91 ppm, due to the effect of electron withdrawing from oxygen atom, which causes a decrease in the electron density around the proton and subsequently resulting to deshielding of the nucleus of the proton by moving downfield (Fig. 1). The ^{13}C NMR of the ligand L1L2 was used as complementary to further ascertain the structure of the ligand. This spectrum is characterised by downfield peak at 169.6 ppm corresponding to CO. The aromatic carbons observed at 149.6 and 132.1 ppm are due to C-Ar while the remaining aromatic carbons due to CH-Ar were observed at 127.9, 116.6, 115.2 and 113.5 ppm.

Figure 1: ^1H -NMR spectrum of the ligand **L1H2**

The functional groups in the ligands were studied in the range of $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ of IR. The FT-IR spectrum of L1H2 showed a characteristic band at 1636 cm^{-1} which was assigned to the $\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretching vibration, while bands at 3403 and 3171 cm^{-1} were consistent with the presence of O-H and N-H stretches, respectively (see experimental section). The mass spectrum obtained from L1H2 gave rise to peaks at (m/z): 152, 136, and 120 corresponding to the $\{\text{M}^+\}$, $\{\text{M}^+\text{-OH}\}$ and $\{\text{M}^+\text{-NH}_2\text{OH}\}$ fragments, respectively.

The ^1H NMR spectrum of L2H2 (Fig. 2) showed a singlet signal at 5.50 ppm associated with the NH_2 group, two double doublets at 6.51 with J value of 8.5 Hz and 7.41 ppm with J value of 8.6 Hz were assigned to the aromatic protons, while singlets at 8.60 and 10.71 ppm corresponding to protons belonging to the amide and OH groups, respectively. The ^{13}C NMR of the ligand L2H2 has two different aromatic carbon (C-Ar and CH-Ar). This spectrum is characterised by peak at 152.0 and 119.6 ppm For C-Ar linked to CO and NH_2 respectively while two other peaks observed at 128.7 and 113.1 correspond to the two equivalent CH-Ar carbons. The CO peak appeared downfield at 165.5 due to the effect of electronegative oxygen atom.

Figure 2: ^1H -NMR spectrum of the ligand **L2H2**

The FT-IR spectrum of L2H2 showed a characteristic band at 1645 cm^{-1} which was assigned to the $\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretching vibration, while bands at 3410 and 3332 cm^{-1} were consistent with the presence of O-H and N-H stretches, respectively (see experimental section).

The mass spectrum of the ligand L2H2 revealed a molecular ion peak at (m/z): 152, 134, and 120 corresponding to the $\{\text{M}^+\}$, $\{\text{M}^+\text{-OH}\}$ and $\{\text{M}^+\text{-NH}_2\text{OH}\}$ fragments, respectively.

The ligand 4-amino-2-(methoxy)phenylhydroxamic acid (L3H2) showed a singlet signal at 3.78 ppm due to three protons of the $-\text{OCH}_3$ group, and another single at 5.69 ppm associated with the NH_2 functional group. A multiplet at 6.21 ppm and two doublets centred at 7.52 ppm ($J = 8.2$ Hz) corresponding to the aromatic protons were also observed. Singlets at 8.78 and 10.11 ppm are due to protons belonging to the amide and OH groups, respectively (Fig. 3).

The ^{13}C NMR of the L3H2 showed CO peak at 164.4 ppm and the aromatic carbon linked to it appeared at 158.8 ppm. The aromatic carbon attached to amine and that OMe were observed at 153.3 and 96.3, respectively was used as complementary to further ascertain the structure of the ligand. This spectrum is characterised by peak at 164.8 and 160.2 ppm corresponding to $\text{C}=\text{N}$ and $\text{C}-\text{OH}$. The other aromatic carbons were observed at 132.3–106.4 ppm, and these accounted for all the carbons within the molecules with some degree of similarity in their chemical environment. Methoxy carbon was observed at 55.6 ppm in the up-field region.

Figure 3: ^1H -NMR spectrum of the ligand L3H2

The FT-IR spectrum of L3H2 showed a characteristic band at 1619 cm^{-1} which was assigned to the $\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretching vibration, while bands at 3343 and 3316 cm^{-1} were consistent with the presence of $\text{O}-\text{H}$ and $\text{N}-\text{H}$ stretches, respectively (see experimental section).

The mass spectrum of the ligand L2H2 revealed a molecular ion peak at (m/z): 182, 166, and 150 corresponding to the $\{\text{M}^+\}$, $\{\text{M}^+-\text{H}_2\text{N}\}$ and $\{\text{M}^+-\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\}$ fragments, respectively.

The ^1H NMR spectrum of the L4H3 (Fig. 4) showed nine distinct peaks, and they accounted for all the protons within the compound. The hydroxamate and salicylaldehyde (OH) protons appeared downfield at 12.85 and 11.28 ppm respectively as single peaks. Singlets at 9.08 ppm corresponding to protons belonging to the amide. The imine ($\text{HC}=\text{N}$) proton was observed at 8.99 ppm region of the spectrum. The aromatic protons were observed between 7.00 and 7.88 ppm. The ^{13}C NMR spectrum of the ligand L4H3 is characterised by peak at 164.9 and 164.1 ppm corresponding to CO and $\text{C}=\text{N}$ carbons of the carbonyl and azomethine respectively. The appearance of these carbons in the downfield region is due to the effect of electronegative oxygen and nitrogen atoms respectively. The other aromatic carbons were observed at 160.7 – 117.1 ppm, and these accounted for all the carbons within the molecules with some degree of similarity in their chemical environment.

Figure 4: ^1H NMR of N-hydroxy-4-((2-hydroxybenzyl)amino)benzamide (L4H3)

The IR spectrum of the ligand L4H3 showed a band at 1617 cm^{-1} , which is assignable to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretching vibration [24]. This ligand also exhibited a distinct peak corresponding to the amide (NHOH) functional group, with vibrational frequencies observed at 3277 cm^{-1} for the $\nu(\text{OH})$ bond stretching and 2699 cm^{-1} for the $\nu(\text{NH})$ bond stretching [25]. Additionally, vibrational frequencies for the $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ stretching of the salicylaldehyde appeared at 3026 cm^{-1} . The MS-EI spectra of L4H3 revealed a parent molecular ion peak at $m/z = 256.08$ corresponds to the $\{\text{M}^+\}$, Other fragments of the ligand were also observed at $m/z = 2040.23$, 224.32 , 196.43 and 77.37 correspond to $\{\text{M} - \text{OH}\}^+$, $\{\text{M} - \text{H}_2\text{NO}\}^+$, $\{\text{M} - \text{CH}_2\text{NO}_2\}^+$ and $\{\text{C}_6\text{H}_6\}^+$ respectively.

Antibacterial Evaluation

The free ligands were screened (*in vitro*) for their antimicrobial potential against some selected pathogenic bacteria: Gram-positive (*S. aureus* and *S. pyogenes*), Gram-negative (*S. typhi* and *E. coli*) and Fungal specie (*Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans*) using disc diffusion method [26]. The results obtained are presented in Table 1. The values of zone inhibition of the compounds against the tested organism were compared with that of standard antibiotics (ciprofloxacin for bacteria and Ketazol for fungi). The ligands 2-aminophenyl hydroxamic acid and 4-aminophenyl hydroxamic acid showed considerable activity against *candida albican* with zone of inhibition of 35.0 ± 0.0 and 30.0 ± 0.0 mm respectively at concentration of 30 mg/mL. Similarly, the ligand 4-amino-2-methoxyphenyl hydroxamic acid presented zone of inhibition of 20.4 ± 0.2 , and 20.1 ± 0.1 mm at concentration of 30 and 20 mg/mL against *S. aureus*, and 20.2 ± 0.2 mm, on *S. pyogenes* at the concentration of 30 mg/mL. The control drugs shows slightly better antimicrobial activity than the best of the ligands. Based on the insights obtained from their biological performance the best ligands were subjected to computational studies.

Table 1: In-vitro antimicrobial activities of Ligands

Compounds	Conc. (mg/mL)	Antimicrobial activity with zone of inhibition (mm)					
		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. pyogenes</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	<i>Candida albicans</i>
L1H2	30	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	10.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	10.0±0.0 ^a	35.0±0.0 ^a
	20	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	10.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	10.0±0.0 ^a	15.0±0.0 ^b
	10	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^b	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^b	10.0±0.0 ^c
L2H2	30	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	10.0±0.0 ^a	10.0±0.0 ^a	30.0±0.0 ^a
	20	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	10.0±0.0 ^a	10.0±0.0 ^a	20.0±0.0 ^b
	10	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	10.0±0.0 ^a	10.0±0.0 ^a	10.0±0.0 ^c
L3H2	30	25.0±0.0 ^a	20.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	10.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a
	20	20.0±0.0 ^b	10.0±0.0 ^b	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^b	0.0±0.0 ^a
	10	10.0±0.0 ^c	10.0±0.0 ^b	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^b	0.0±0.0 ^a
L4H3	30	20.0±0.0 ^a	20.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	10.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a
	20	20.0±0.0 ^b	10.0±0.0 ^b	0.0±0.0 ^a	10.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a
	10	10.0±0.0 ^c	10.0±0.0 ^b	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^b	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a
Ciprofloxacin	30	35.0±0.0 ^a	30.0±0.0 ^a	30.0±0.0 ^a	35.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a
	20	35.0±0.0 ^a	30.0±0.0 ^a	20.0±0.0 ^b	30.0±0.0 ^b	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a
	10	20.0±0.0 ^b	10.0±0.0 ^b	10.0±0.0 ^c	20.0±0.0 ^c	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a
Ketazol	30	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	30.0±0.0 ^a	37.0±0.0 ^a
	20	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	25.0±0.0 ^b	30.0±0.0 ^b
	10	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	0.0±0.0 ^a	20.0±0.0 ^c	20.0±0.0 ^c

ADMET Studies

The ADMET properties of the selected compounds were evaluated using QikProp descriptors, with emphasis on parameters relevant to drug-likeness, oral absorption, permeability, distribution, metabolic liability, and cardiotoxicity risk. Overall, the compounds displayed acceptable drug-likeness with no Lipinski violations, moderate-to-high predicted oral absorption, and favourable hERG inhibition profiles (Table 2).

Table 2: ADMET properties of the synthesized compounds

Title	CNS	Human Oral Absorption	Lipinski Rule Of Five	PSA	% Human Oral Absorption	QPPCaco	QPPMDCK	QPlogBB	QPlogHERG	QPlogPo/w	QPlogS
L1H2	-1	2	0	86.895	66.594	226.251	99.252	-0.98	-3.633	-0.426	-0.475
L2H2	-2	2	0	90.956	61.852	152.342	64.725	-1.146	-3.683	-0.711	-0.799
L3H2	-2	2	0	95.928	63.518	168.036	71.962	-1.227	-3.732	-0.556	-1.273

All compounds showed zero Lipinski Rule-of-Five violations (Rule of Five = 0), indicating that the molecular size and polarity fall within acceptable drug-like space. Molecular weights were within a drug-like range, with all the three compounds showing low molecular weights. The polar surface area (PSA) ranged from ~86.9 to 95.9 Å², indicating

moderate-to-high polarity. This PSA range supports systemic exposure and solubility but may limit CNS penetration, which aligns with the predicted CNS scores discussed below.

In addition, the compounds showed clear differences in predicted ADMET behaviour. These amino-substituted scaffolds demonstrated acceptable aqueous solubility (QPlogS \sim -0.48 to -1.27). Lipophilicity values (QPlogPo/w) further supported this trend, with the compounds being highly hydrophilic (negative logP). Predicted permeability values indicated that all compounds possessed at least moderate intestinal permeability. Human oral absorption was predicted to be moderate for all the compounds (\sim 62–67%). Distribution parameters suggested limited CNS penetration for all compounds, supported by negative QPlogBB values and CNS scores between -1 and -2. Importantly, all compounds showed low predicted hERG inhibition risk, with QPlogHERG values indicating an overall favourable cardiotoxicity profile.

Molecular Docking Studies

Staphylococcus aureus (PDB ID: 3G7B):

Molecular docking of the three ligands into the *Staphylococcus aureus* protein target (PDB ID: 3G7B) revealed distinct binding modes, hydrogen bond geometries, hydrophobic contacts, and solvent exposure patterns. The docking scores obtained in the present study ranged from -5.735 to -5.032, L3H2 showing the strongest affinity and L1H2 the weakest. The binding pocket is primarily defined by residues Thr173 and Asp81. Thr173 is a polar but partially buried residue, while Asp81 is negatively charged and located near the pocket entrance, making it relatively more solvent-exposed. As noted by earlier structural analyses, acidic residues such as Asp81 at binding interfaces are often immersed in crystal water networks and behave as extensions of the protein hydration shell, meaning that ligand binding must compete with existing water molecules [27]. These characteristics fundamentally influence hydrogen bond quality and ligand orientation within the binding site.

The ligand L3H2 achieved the highest docking score of -5.735, which correlates with its extensive and geometrically favourable hydrogen bond network (Fig. 5). A single hydrogen bond was formed with Thr173 at a distance of approximately 2.7 to 3.0 Å. Additionally, two hydrogen bonds were established with Asp81, one to each carboxylate oxygen, with typical distances within 2.6 to 2.9 Å. Beyond hydrogen bonding, the methoxy group contributes hydrophobic and van der Waals contacts with nearby aliphatic residues such as leucine and valine, enhancing the burial of nonpolar surface area. Previous studies have specifically highlighted that methoxy-substituted ligands play a particularly important role in stabilizing binding through hydrophobic effects [28]. Importantly, both Thr173 and Asp81 are fully engaged, indicating deeper penetration into the binding pocket. This reduced solvent exposure of the ligand correlates with a favourable entropic contribution to binding. The combination of excellent hydrogen bond geometry, bidentate interaction with Asp81, and methoxy-mediated hydrophobic packing collectively explains the highest binding affinity observed in this series.

Figure 5: Ligand L3H2 interaction with PDB 3G7B

Ligand 4-aminophenyl hydroxamic acid (L2H2) presents an interesting comparison to 4-amino-2methoxy (L3H2), as it also forms three hydrogen bonds: one with Thr173 and two with Asp81. Despite this identical hydrogen bond count, its docking score of -5.173 is noticeably lower. The unsubstituted phenyl ring provides only moderate π -alkyl or π - π stacking interactions with potential aromatic residues such as tyrosine or phenylalanine, but these are less optimized than in the methoxy-containing analog. Furthermore, the absence of the methoxy group reduces nonpolar surface burial, increasing the solvent-accessible area of the bound ligand and thereby lowering binding affinity. Although the hydrogen bond count is the same, the overall geometry of these bonds may be less ideal due to the rigid orientation of the phenyl ring, resulting in suboptimal distances or angles (Fig. 6). Thus, the reduced docking score reflects poorer hydrophobic complementarity rather than a deficiency in polar interactions. This observation is consistent with the concept that hydrophobic enclosure is essential for translating polar interactions into favorable binding energetics [29].

Figure 6: Ligand L2H2 interaction with PDB 3G7B

The ligand 2-aminophenyl hydroxamic acid (L1H2) forms the highest number of hydrogen bonds among the three compounds, with one interaction involving Thr173 and three separate hydrogen bonds with Asp81. Nevertheless, it yields the weakest docking score of -5.032 (Fig. 7). This apparent contradiction can be explained by examining the quality rather than the quantity of these interactions. It is likely that one or more of the hydrogen bonds exhibit suboptimal geometry, such as angles below 120 degrees or distances exceeding 3.3 Å. Additionally, the ortho-amino group may force a twisted or strained binding conformation that reduces overall complementarity with the pocket. Hydrophobic contributions are likely minimal, as the multiple amino groups dominate the ligand's polarity, reducing favorable nonpolar burial. From a solvation perspective, the ligand may be exposed to solvent-exposed despite its numerous hydrogen bonds, incurring a higher desolvation penalty that offsets the enthalpic gains. This pattern directly illustrates what Friesner and colleagues [29] described as the "hydrogen bonding penalty": when polar interactions are formed with poor geometry or without adequate hydrophobic enclosure, the energy gained does not compensate for the cost of desolvating the ligand and protein in an aqueous environment. Consequently, this case clearly demonstrates that hydrogen bond count alone is not predictive of binding affinity, and that geometric quality, desolvation effects, and hydrophobic interactions are equally critical.

Figure 7: Ligand L1H2 interaction with PDB 3G7B

Summing up the three ligands in this work, a clear structure-activity relationship emerges. The highest scoring ligand, L3H2, achieves optimal hydrogen bond geometry and hydrophobic burial, in agreement with reported roles of methoxy groups in enhancing binding. In contrast, L2H2 retains the same polar contacts but suffers from reduced hydrophobic complementarity. L1H2 demonstrates that excessive hydrogen bonding without proper geometry or hydrophobic support can be counterproductive, consistent with the hydrogen bonding penalty considerations [29]. These findings underscore that successful ligand design for the 3G7B binding site must balance hydrogen bond quality, hydrophobic interactions, and minimal solvent exposure rather than simply maximizing interaction counts.

***Candida albicans* (PDB ID: 4HOE):**

The crystal structure of *C. albicans* DHFR complexed with NADPH and a propargyl-linked antifolate (PDB ID: 4HOE) was solved at 1.76 Å resolution and has served as a benchmark for structure-based antifungal design [30] (G-Dayananandan et al., 2014). The binding site of antifolate was used to explore the ligands synthesised in this work. The docking scores obtained ranged from -5.659 to -4.626, with 4-amino-2-methoxyphenyl hydroxamic acid (L3H2) showing the strongest affinity and 4-aminophenyl hydroxamic acid (L2H2) the weakest. The binding pocket of *C. albicans* DHFR is characterized by several conserved residues that have been previously implicated in antifolate binding, including Phe36, Ile112, and Trp27 [30]. Notably, the binding site architecture differs from bacterial and human DHFR homologs, offering opportunities for selective inhibition [31] (Mujwar & Tripathi, 2022).

Ligand 4-amino-2-methoxy exhibited the most favourable docking score of -5.659, representing the strongest binding affinity in the series (Fig. 8). This ligand formed a hydrogen bond with Trp27, a residue that sits near the solvent-exposed region of the binding pocket. The engagement of Trp27 may contribute to binding by anchoring the ligand at the entrance of the active site, potentially reducing conformational flexibility. Previous studies on propargyl-linked antifolates have emphasized that the shape and distribution of polar functionality are critical for achieving potent antifungal activity, and even small changes in substitution patterns can significantly alter binding affinity [30].

Figure 8: Ligand L3H2 interaction with PDB 4HOE

Ligand 2-aminophenyl hydroxamic acid (L1H2) yielded a docking score of -4.815 (Fig. 9), placing it as the second most potent binder in the series. This ligand formed a hydrogen bond with Gln32, a residue that has not been prominently featured in previous crystallographic analyses of 4HOE but may play a role in stabilizing certain ligand alignments. The interaction with Gln32 suggests that this ligand adopts a binding mode distinct from that of the higher-scoring compounds, perhaps shifting toward a more solvent-exposed region of the pocket. Additionally, L1H2 maintained a hydrogen bond with Ile112 and a π - π stacking interaction with Phe36. The preservation of the Phe36 interaction across all three ligands in this study underscores the central role of this aromatic residue in antifolate binding to *C. albicans* DHFR. This finding is consistent with structural studies of related DHFR enzymes, where conserved phenylalanine residues (Phe31 and Phe34 in human DHFR) are known to form critical hydrophobic contacts with the pyrimidine ring of antifolates [32].

Figure 9: Ligand L1H2 interaction with PDB 4HOE

Ligand 4-amino-phenyl hydroxamic (L2H2) produced the weakest docking score of -4.626 , despite forming multiple hydrogen bonds and an aromatic interaction (Fig. 10). Similar to L1H2, this ligand engaged Gln32 through a hydrogen bond and also interacted with Ile112. Notably, the interaction with Ile112 was characterized as an "aromatic H-bond" in the interaction table, suggesting that the phenyl ring participates in a specialized polar- π interaction rather than a conventional hydrogen bond. The para-aminophenyl substitution pattern may position the amino group in a region of the binding pocket that is less optimally shaped for hydrogen bonding compared to the ortho isomer. Additionally, the absence of interactions with Trp27 or additional stabilizing contacts may contribute to the reduced binding affinity. It is worth noting that the docking scores for both L1H2 and L2H2 (-4.815 and -4.626 , respectively) fall within a range that may still be considered moderate for initial screening hits, but they are substantially lower than the top score of -5.659 achieved by L3H2. This gap suggests that the methoxy group and the specific positioning of hydrogen bond donors and acceptors are critical for achieving high-affinity binding to *C. albicans* DHFR.

Figure 10: Ligand L2H2 interaction with PDB 4HOE

Conclusion

In this study, Four hydroxamic acid ligands (L1H2, L2H2, L3H2 and L4H3) were successfully synthesized from reaction of corresponding aromatic esters and hydroxylamine tetraoxosulphate(VI) and were characterised using various technique relevant for the conformation of molecular structures such as FTIR, elemental analysis, melting point, solubility tests, and NMR, confirmed the successful formation of the ligands. The compounds were stable at room temperature in the solid state and soluble in the common organic solvents CHCl_3 , EtOH, MeOH, DMF, and DMSO.

Biological evaluation demonstrated that the *in vitro* antimicrobial screening of the ligands against some selected Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria showed that the complex is more active than the ligand, and the activity was found to be concentration-dependent.

The synthesized ligands displayed a balanced and developable ADMET profile, combining acceptable aqueous solubility, moderate membrane permeability, moderate predicted oral absorption, low metabolic liability, and favourable hERG safety. Within these ligands, L1H2 emerged as the most promising candidate based on its superior solubility and comparatively higher permeability.

The highest scoring ligand in the molecular docking studies is L3H2 which achieved optimal hydrogen bond geometry and hydrophobic burial, in agreement with reported roles of methoxy groups in enhancing binding. In contrast, L2H2 retains the same polar contacts but suffers from reduced hydrophobic complementarity. L1H2 demonstrates that excessive hydrogen bonding without proper geometry or hydrophobic support can be counterproductive, consistent with the hydrogen bonding penalty considerations. These findings underscore that successful ligand design for the 3G7B binding site must balance hydrogen bond quality, hydrophobic interactions, and minimal solvent exposure rather than simply maximizing interaction counts.

Observing the three ligands in the 4HOE receptor site of propargylated antifolates, a clear structure-activity relationship emerges. Ligand H3H2 achieves the highest docking score through a combination. The similarity between the interaction profile of the ligands and that of the validated ligand provides confidence that the docking poses obtained in this study are relevant to the actual binding mode.

Authors' Contributory Statements

All authors contributed substantially to the conception, design, and execution of the research work. Experimental synthesis, characterization studies, Funding acquisition, and data acquisition were carried out by M. B. Fugu, computational studies was perfumed by Al- amin A. Mohammed, Data interpretation, manuscript drafting, critical review, and editing were jointly performed by all authors. All authors have read and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare that they have no known financial or personal conflicts of interest that could have influenced the work reported in this manuscript.

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